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ABSTRACT

Drug discovery and development is one of the oldest practices in human history. The process of drug development has evolved throughout history to protect human health and treat disease. The first use of drugs was mostly carried out by empirical methods, and the ancient civilizations of Mesopotamia, Egypt and China laid the foundations of pharmacopoeia (Balick & Cox, 1997). With the development of modern chemistry in the 19th century, the first pure active compounds such as morphine and aspirin were isolated. With the development of synthesis techniques, the era of synthetic drugs began (Newman & Cragg, 2020). The discovery of antibiotics and the beginning of controlled clinical trials in the mid-20th century established the modern drug development paradigm (Sneider, 2005).

Computer-aided drug design (CADD) has become an influential area of research, especially with the development of high-throughput screening (HTS) and computational methods since the late 20th century (Lipinski & Hopkins, 2004). CADD has begun to play a critical role in drug discovery and development, enabling faster, more targeted, and lower-cost design of new drugs. These approaches include structure-based drug design (SBDD), which is based on the three-dimensional structure of the target protein, and ligand-based drug design (LBDD), which is based on known active molecules (Schneider & Baringhaus, 2008). Virtual screening approaches allow rapid screening of large compound libraries (Lounnas et al., 2013). The Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR) method, which models the mathematical relationship between the molecular structures of chemical compounds and their biological activities, is especially used in toxicity and activity predictions (Cherkasov et al., 2014). By using CADD strategies, the binding forms and energies of molecules with target proteins are calculated (Meng, Zhang, Mezei, & Cui, 2011). With the help of molecular dynamics simulations performed against time, more realistic results are produced. Especially in the last century, CADD, which has become a high-tech process by integrating with scientific disciplines, enables systematic modeling of drug candidates. Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) methods have revolutionized drug discovery. In particular, deep learning-based generative models are used in the automatic design of new compounds (Zhavoronkov et al., 2019). Additionally, tools such as AlphaFold 2 have greatly accelerated structure-based design processes by predicting target protein structures with high accuracy (Jumper et al., 2021).

This report focuses on the historical development starting from traditional herbal treatments to the modern pharmaceutical industry and CADD. The integration of CADD technology into drug development processes, its evolution, basic approaches, current application areas and the integration of artificial intelligence into the system were examined. It was emphasized how advances in artificial intelligence, big data and molecular simulation technologies will affect drug discovery processes in the coming years.

KEYWORDS

Drug discovery, computer aided drug design (CADD), molecular modeling, QSAR, docking, molecular dynamics, artificial intelligence

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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